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Spiders' biodiversity, ecological significance, activity density, behavior in obtaining food and incidence with their preys

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Abstract

In this review, we discuss recent studies on the spider's adaptation to various habitats, their role in controlling arthropod pests and their significance as bio-indicators of environmental health. This article looks at spiders and their capacity to adapt to a variety of environments, as well as their role in arthropod pest control and how they can be protected from extinction and their significance as biomarkers of environmental health. Also investigates spider-environment interactions, such as their roles in ecosystems, behaviors, habitat preferences, and partnerships with other creatures. It examines spider populations, community dynamics, and the effects of environmental changes on spider diversity and distribution. Review articles may also underline the importance of protecting spider diversity and the necessity for immediate study to understand and safeguard these crucial organisms. This article investigates the activity of spiders inhabiting land of organic and conventional plants, the management effect of different forms of vegetation structure, soil fertility management, spider species biodiversity in different vegetable crops, in certain medicinal and ornamental plants. Moreover, throw light on the impact of some new Acaricides assessing spider biodiversity and seasonal dynamics.

Introduction

Spiders are ancient arthropods from the Arachnida class that date back around 350 million years. The largest order, Araneae, ranks ninth in terms of species diversity. Spiders range in size from small to huge, have distinct characteristics, and are typically found in terrestrial areas (Turnbull, 1973; Preston, 1984 and Nyffeler and Benz, 1987).

Spiders play an important role in the environment's bottom food chain, contributing to ecological balance and

acting as reliable bio-indicators of natural ecosystems, Misal *et al.* (2019). Tahir and Butt (2009) discovered that field management practices had a substantial effect on spider species abundance and dispersal.

Spiders, as generalist predators, play important roles in food webs and communities (Bucher *et al.*, 2015; Stokmane and Spungis, 2016 and Ludwig *et al.*, 2018). Spiders are crucial in ecosystem management and may act as biological control agents (Riechert and Bishop, 1990). Spider variety is

crucial for understanding community-level biological organization. According to Hill (1973), greater species diversity leads to a healthier and more complex community due to increased interactions and system stability, implying favorable environmental circumstances.

The diversity of a habitat's physical and biological components determines its complexity. More complex ecosystems often provide a broader selection of shelters, food, and reproduction sites, resulting in increased biodiversity. We examined structural factors such as leaf quantity, plant size, herbivores incidence, and prey availability, as measured by insect richness. Spider richness was found to be positively correlated with insect richness, highlighting the relevance of prey diversity in supporting predator groups. However, the negative relationship between spider abundance and leaf number suggests that denser foliage may limit access for some spider species or promote specialist dominance (Reis *et al.*, 2025).

Spiders, a diverse and ecologically important group of arthropods, are sensitive to habitat structure, with species composition usually reflecting resource availability and microhabitat complexity (Podgaiski and Rodrigues, 2017 and Potapov *et al.*, 2022). Vegetation structure influences spider assemblages by affecting microclimate, prey abundance, and web-building opportunities (Souza and Martins, 2004, 2005 and Malumbres-Olarte *et al.*, 2013). This includes plant density, height, and species composition. Spider diversity is often higher in areas with greater vegetative complexity, most likely due to the presence of microhabitats and ecological niches that minimize interspecific competition and improve prey capture efficiency (Barton *et al.*, 2017).

Review articles on spiders explore their biological diversity, ecological significance, including their role in controlling insect populations and serving as a food source. Spiders are important predators of many arthropod pests in agriculture.

Spiders adapt to various habitats:

El-Hennawy (2017) created a checklist of Egyptian spider species (405 species, 204 taxa, and 41 families) that includes scientific names and distribution localities (geographical areas in Egypt). All adults and juveniles were identified to the species level or morph species. Specimens were recognized to the family, genus and species levels using different specific keys such as Kaston (1978), Roberts (1987), Levi (2002), Oger (2002), Prószyński (2003), Huber (2005) and El-Hennawy (2017). Collected spiders were kept in glass vials containing 75 % ethyl alcohol and some droplets of glycerin.

1. Spider populations associated with different types of cultivation and different vegetable crops:

In this study, Habashy *et al.* (2005) studied the influence of various vegetable crop production methods, such as intercropping, monoculture, and crop rotation, on activity density and spider biodiversity in Fayoum (Middle Egypt).

1.1. Effect of intercropping:

It is a traditional agricultural method that involves growing many crops in the same region at the same time which provides numerous benefits, can prevent disease, pests, preserve soil fertility, and maximize land productivity (Ghosh, 2004; Rizk and Mikhail (2000) and Rizk *et al.* 2017). Spiders sampled by using pitfall traps, the total number of spiders obtained were 28, 30 and 44, from intercropping tomato/squash, tomato /pumpkin and pepper/eggplant, respectively. Four families were recorded, Lycosidae,

Linyphiidae, Philodromidae and Theridiidae. Lycosidae spiders dominated intercropping cultivation with a percentage of 89.29, 83.33, and 68.9%, respectively. Weis Fogh's (1948) identified Lycosidae as a constant family; however, Weigmann's (1973) technique classed it as dominant. According to Ahmed (2003), Lycosidae constituted the vast majority of the ground spider population, accounting for 83.77% and having a high prevalence. The highest number of spiders was obtained in August. Linyphiidae was considered the dominant family in pepper/eggplant intercropping, this is in accordance with that of Coll and Bottrell (1995) who studied the effect of intercropping bean/maize and reported that spiders of the Linyphiidae and Araneidae families were more common in dicultures. According to Wallwork (1976), spider populations have different preferences for microclimatic conditions, which can fluctuate over a species' reproductive cycle. Rizk *et al.* (2015) discovered that complex vegetation structures increase prey diversity for spiders, resulting in rapid population growth and higher spider densities. Ghabbour *et al.* (1999) attribute variation in plant numbers to factors such as shade, humidity, water requirements, and plant density influences the abundance of spider prey.

1.2. Effect of monoculture:

Monoculture, is the technique of cultivating only one crop at a time in a given field, is widely used, but its sustainability is questioned, particularly if the same crop is cultivated every year (Rizk, 2015 and Rizk *et al.*, 2017). Habashy *et al.* (2005) recorded eight families from monoculture cultivation, they were, Lycosidae, Dictynidae, Philodromidae, Linyphiidae, Miturgidae, Thomisidae, Philodromidae, Salticidae and Theridiidae. The total numbers of spiders were 29, 52&13

from plots of cowpea, cabbage and tomato, with ratios of 68.9, 84.6 and 69.2%, respectively. Ghabbour *et al.* (1999) expressed that the high numbers of spiders occurred in cabbage plot, was due to the dense of cabbage leaves produced shade and humidity which affect abundance of spiders. Also, Rizk *et al.* (2009) studied the increasing number of spiders in clover monoculture systems, which could be due to the highest numbers of herbivores and detritivores groups, this deduction is supported by Bardwell and Averill (1997) and Malony *et al.* (2003), who demonstrated that spiders preyed on collembola and small dipterous larvae located in the ground. The total numbers obtained spiders were 29, 52 and 13 collected from cowpea, cabbage, and tomato monoculture, with ratios of 68.9, 84.6 and 69.2%, respectively. Lycosidae family was the dominant in monoculture cultivation, this result is in accordance with Ghallab *et al.* (2005) who studied the distribution of the most dominant family Lycosidae in four cultivated systems, where individuals of Lycosidae accounted 10.4 % in mono-cultured tomato and showed higher frequency than in the intercropping cultivated system tomato/squash and tomato/pumpkin which recorded 6.2 and 6.4%, respectively. Lycosidae was the dominant family in monoculture; it was classified by Weis Fogh's (1948) and Weigmann's (1973) as a constant and dominant family. Review articles on spiders explore their biological diversity, ecological significance, including their role in controlling insect populations and serving as a food source. In addition, Habashy *et al.* (2005) found that Dictynidae dominated in cowpea, while Philodromidae dominated in tomato. Both Linyphiidae and Miturgidae were found in cowpea and cabbage.

Thomisidae was subdominant (7.69%) in monoculture tomato; however, it disappeared from cowpea and cabbage. Cabbage's microclimate was a big influence to spider density.

1.3. Crop rotation:

Crop rotation is important to sustainable cropping systems. A well-designed crop generates diversity, improves soil conditions, and increases soil fauna and fertility, Rizk *et al.* (2006). According to Rizk and El-Gayar (2014), crop rotation is improving soil fertility, reduces pest buildup, lowering the danger of weather damage, reducing reliance on agricultural chemicals, and increasing net earnings. Habashy *et al.* (2005) found that six families were recorded from crop rotation cultivation; they were Lycosidae, Dictynidae, Philodromidae, Linyphiidae, Miturgidae and Theridiidae. The garlic cultivated after cowpea, radish after green pepper, and spinach after tomato; spiders collected were 11, 19, and 14 spiders, respectively. The garlic plot had the fewest individuals and diversity of spider species, while radish plot had the highest individuals and diversity. Crop rotation frequently lowers individual insect outbreaks, especially in garlic. Lycosidae was the most prevalent family, with ratios of 63.6, 68.4, and 57.1% in crop rotation of garlic, followed by radish then spinach, respectively. Zaki and Ali (2019) proved that individuals of Lycosidae represent 70% of ground spiders collected from onion farms using pitfall traps. Moreover, Rizk *et al.* (2002) demonstrated that the chemical composition of plants or the volatile garlic deterrents may have an effect on spiders, while Edwards and Lofty (1969) stated that crop rotation diminishes species diversity much more dramatically. Variations in sun and shade have a considerable impact on the horizontal dispersion patterns of

various pests, altering spider development rates.

2. Soil fertility management and spider species diversity:

Rizk *et al.* (2008) compared the occurrence of different spider families in cucumber plantation treated with three different fertilizations: Effective microorganism (EM), mixture of some chelated micro-elements (Zinc, copper, manganese and iron, each of 12% chelating on EDTA of 400gm/feddan) (Mix.) and a combination of the two previous fertilizers in equal rate.

According to the manual application APNAN (2007), EM are not pesticides and thus do not contain chemicals that could be construed as microbial in oculant's functions as biological control measures in suppressing and/or controlling pests through the introduction of beneficial microorganisms into the plant environment. As a result, pests and pathogens are inhibited or controlled naturally by boosting the competitive and antagonistic activities of microorganisms in EM inoculants. The total number of spiders sampled by using pitfall traps, the number of individuals trapped dependent on the locomotors activity and is taken as number per trap, therefore called "activity density" (Kromp, 1990 and Mikhaeil and Ghabbour, 1993). A total of 322 spider species were caught in three different treatments and the untreated one (Control). They were identified in 8 families and 14 genera and at least 15 species. Generic richness was dominated by the Linyphiidae (4 genera) followed by the Lycosidae (3 genera). The families Titanoecidae, Gnaphosidae, Miturgidae and Theridiidae were monotypes among trap catches. *Wadicosa fidelis* (Lycosidae) was the most abundant species.

- **Spiders collected from plot of Trace –Elements:** they were two families, 5

genera and 5 species; Lycosidae {*Wadicosa fidelis*, *Pardosa* sp. and G3; Linyphiidae {*Bathyphantes extricatus* and G4} .

- **Spiders collected from untreated plot (control):** they were five families, 7 genera and 7 species, Lycosidae (*Wadicosa fidelis*) , Titanoecidae (*Nurscica albomaculata*, Linyphiidae {*Prinerigone vagans* (Savigny), *Erigone dentipalpis*, *Bathyphantes extricate*; Philodromidae (*Thanatus albini*) and Salticidae(G₁).

- **Spiders collected from plot of Mix.:** They were five families, 8genera & 8 species; Lycosidae (*Wadicosa fidelis* and *Pardosa* sp.) , Linyphiidae (*Bathyphantes extricates* and G₄), Philodromidae (*Thanatus albini*), Gnaphosidae (*Trachyzelotes* sp.) and Salticidae (G₁ and G₂) .

- **Spiders collected from plot of EM:** They were six families, 10 genera & 10 species; Lycosidae (*Wadicosa fidelis* and G₃), Linyphiidae (*Prinerigone vagans*, *Erigone dentipalpis* and G₄), Philodromidae (*Thanatus* sp.), Miturgidae (*Cheiracanthium* sp.), Theridiidae (*Steatoda erigoniformis*) and Salticidae (G₁ and G₂).

2.1. Relative abundance of spider families:

Rizk *et al.* (2008) found that, Family Lycosidae was the most common in the three treatments and in the control. It was accounted for 82.56, 90.79, 80.19 and 67.79% in EM, Trace -Elements, Mixture and control plots, respectively. It was considered a constant family according to the system adapted by Weis Fogh (1948) and Eudominant family according to Weigmann's system (1973). Linyphidae was considered an accidental family.

2.2. Spider sex ratio and life stages:

The pitfall-traps yield 163 male and 88 female spiders; of sex ratio 64.9male to 35.1% female, the adult of totaled 79.2 % of all spiders trapped. Species diversity recorded from the organic

plots, EM and Mixture , were 10 and 8 species, respectively; they were more than the Trace-elements and control which recorded 5 and 7 species, respectively .This result is also indicated by Feber *et al.* (1998), who proved that both the number of spiders captured and the species richness of spider samples were higher in organic wheat field than conventional one. So, all species of spiders are sensitive to changes in different types of fertilizers; high number of spiders were noted in the Mixture treatment plot (103 individuals) more than the other treatment which may be due to increase in spider abundance in response to high aphid densities in this time (Habashi *et al.*, 2007). Zaki *et al.* (2021) discovered that fertilizer application promotes plant biomass production, which supports a high number of herbivores and detritivores, hence increasing predator abundance. These findings are consistent with Siemann (1998). Pitfall traps capture more male than female spiders, this result is in accordance with Muma (1975) and Muzika and Twery (1997).

3. Spider occurrence in fields of some medicinal and ornamental plants in Fayoum, Egypt:

Rizk *et al.* (2012) studied the effect of different vegetations of four medicinal and ornamental plants on spider diversity in Fayoum, these plants were: *Egyptian spearmint*, *Mentha niliaca* Jacq, Castorbean, *Ricinus communis*, *Roselle karkadi*. *Hibiscus sabdariffa* and red pepper *Capsicum annum*. Spiders were collected by two methods, by using ground pitfall traps for ground spiders and by shaking method (vegetation beating) for foliage spiders. A total of 315 spiders were collected during the experiment with 52.9 % of them adults; 216 spiders were collected from pitfall traps of 65% were adults. Corresponding values for the

foliage spiders were 99 spiders and 24.5% of them were adults.

3.1. Ground collected spiders:

The ground spiders collected belonged to 11 families and 16 species. Family Lycosidae represented by three species: *Wadicosa fidelis*, *Pardosa injucanda* and *Pardosa* sp.; all were collected by pitfall traps below the four plants under investigation. Vegetation type influenced spider abundance. Spearmint received the lowest number of individuals, 34 individuals, belonged to 4 species and 2 families; Roselle received the greatest number of individuals, 73 individuals, 10 families and 14 species followed by Castor bean plant of 64 individuals, 7 families and 12 species; Red pepper recorded 45 individuals, belonged to 10 families and 13 species. Abo-Zaed *et al.* (2019) conducted a survey of 25 medicinal and aromatic plants in two gardens, Zoheria in Cairo and Orman in Giza Governorates over two years. They registered 18 spiders from 9 families and recorded rose, geranium, chamomile, sweet basil, neem, and *Mentha piperita* the highest spider occurrence, with 52, 39, 35, 28, 20 and 20 individuals, respectively. Marigold and carnation received the fewest spiders, 8 and 10, respectively.

3.2. Aerial collected spiders:

The aerial or foliage collected spiders received from leaves by shaking plants; families Lycosidae, Gnaphosidae, Filistatidae, Titanocidae. Spearmint received the highest spider abundance, of 63 individuals, belonging to 14 species and 10 families. Members of Thomisidae, Dictynidae and Theridiidae were the most frequent taxa on Spearmint plants; they recorded 12, 11 and 10 individuals, respectively, while Roselle plants were free from aerial spiders. The three plantations: Spearmint, Red pepper and Castor bean received five families composed of 63, 29 and 7 individuals, respectively. The

developmental stages of the foliage spiders differed from that of the ground ones. The juveniles were more abundant than the adults, recording 75.7 % of the total collected foliage spiders and the sex ratio was 1.1 male to 1 female. There was, however, a large difference in the composition of spiders and their richness in the two groups. The pitfall method collected more adult spiders and more individual species than did the aerial beating method. Halaj *et al.* (2000) proposed that differences in spider fauna among plant species imply the presence of spider associations based on environmental factors. Previous research has shown that differences in vegetation density, the surface or size of leaves or leaflets, the lack of branch growth and interlacing, and the plant's height and lower length all influence the presence of spiders that use the plant as a shelter (Ghallab, 2013).

4. Preliminary study of the spiders inhabiting ornamental plants in Orman garden, Egypt (Arachnida: Araneae):

Ghallab (2012) surveyed and studied the seasonal abundance of spiders, in the Orman garden, Giza, Egypt for one whole year, from two ornamental plants of different structural composition; the first was a set of Croton trees (*Codiaeum variegatum* L.) near a lake, composed of 28 trees of 2-4 m. height, the second was Lantana shrubs (*Lantana camara* L.) found as hedge nearly of 35m long planted on sandy soil. Spiders were collected by shaking the plants on a sheet or by visual searching of spiders running on the grounds.

4.1. Survey of spiders inhabiting Lantana plants:

A total of 263 spiders were collected from *Lantana* shrubs; they belonged to 13 families, 25 genera and more than 25 species of females totalled 39.5%, while juvenile stages 60.5% and the sex

ratio were 2.1 female : 1 male. The most abundant species were 4 ranked in the top, *Cheiracanthium* sp. (72 individuals), *Philodromus* sp. (44 individuals), *Kochiura aulica* (Koch) (19 individuals) and *Thomisus spinifer* (12 individuals).

4.2. Survey of spiders inhabiting Croton plants:

A total of 304 spiders were collected from Croton trees they could be classified to 10 families, 21 genera and more than 21 species. The collected males and females totalled 53.3%, while juvenile stages 46.7% and the sex ratio was 1.1 female: 1 male. The most dominant species was *Kochiura aulica* (Koch) (64 individuals) followed by *Philodromus* sp. (63 individuals), *Cheiracanthium* sp. (25 individuals), then *Larinioides* sp. (20 individuals).

4.3. Guild composition:

The collected spiders can be divided into seven functional guilds based on their foraging behaviour in the field as described by Uetz *et al.* (1999). They were:

- Hunting spiders (stalkers, ground runners, ambusher, foliage runners)
- Web building spiders (Orb web, space weavers, wandering sheet)

The foliage runner, stalker and ambusher spider guilds were the dominant feeding guilds on Lantana, while the orb web spiders, the space weavers and the ambusher were the dominant feeding guilds on croton trees.

4.4. Faunal similarity of spiders:

Species richness of spiders collected from Croton (304 individuals) is greater than that of Lantana (263 individuals), while the number of spider species greater in Lantana (32 species) than that in Croton (26 species); Lantana and Croton plants had between 9 and 15 unique species, and the common genera were 17 by comparing between the habitats of the two plants, Sørensen's Quotient of similarity (QS) for the two

plants was calculated. It is concluded that the two plants are semi-similar as they recorded 59% of similarity.

5. The effect of some new acaricides on the two spotted spider mites *Tetranychus urticae* on watermelon crops and their side effect on spiders (Araneae):

Rizk *et al.* (2013) studied the efficiency of different pesticides suppressing the population of the two spotted spider mite, *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (TSSM) on watermelon plants. Three biochemical compounds: Yurmak 1.8% EC (Abamectin), Veto 5% EC (Abamectin), and Biofly 30x10³ WP (*Beauvaria bassiana*); three acaricides: Ortus 5% SC (Fenpyroximate), Acarots 5% EW (Fenpyroximate) and Prince 10% EC (Hexythiazox) and two mixture compounds: Nest 20% SC (Abamectin 2% + Spirodiclofen 18%) and Perfect 12% EW (Abamectin 2% + Chlorofenapyr 10%). They applied one time to control *T. urticae* infesting watermelon plants during the experiment period. The different acaricides were effective in controlling TSSM for two weeks after application. Abamectin (biochemical) was effective in reducing TSSM population and revealed less effect on associated predators; while Hexythiazox was harmful and reduced true spider populations.

5.1. Spider assemblages:

A total number of 377 spiders were collected belonged to 8 families, 11 genera and 12 species, the sex ratio was 1 ♀: 3.4 ♂ totalled 53.3%. The more abundant species were *Wadicosa fidelis* Octavius (166 individuals), *Hogna ferox* Lucas (64), *Pardosa* sp₁ (52) and *Pardosa* sp₂ (38) all of family Lycosidae. Rizk *et al.* (2004) indicated that spiders of family Lycosidae are more frequent in pitfall traps and show a certain degree of resistance to acaricides. Family Salticidae was

represented by 2 genera (*Phlegra flavipes* Denis and *Pellenes* sp.). Members of the remaining families Philodromidae, Miturgidae, Linyphidae, Gnaphosidae, Thomisidae and Theridiidae were noted in few numbers by only a single species for each.

5.2. Effect of tested compounds on true spiders associated with *Tetranychus urticae* :

The acaricides Prince (Hexythiazox) and Acarots 5 % E W (fenpyroximate) were the most effective pesticides on predators, whereas the collected spiders recorded 14 & 33 individuals, respectively, Abd-Elhady *et al.* (2011) reported that the use of this compound in the field resulted in severe reduction of the predator, *P. persimilis*. Also, plot treated with Prince, recorded the lowest numbers of the spiders (14 individuals), Rizk *et al.* (2004 and 2005) cited the dangerous of acaricides use on the biodiversity of the true spider fauna. Among the acaricides tested, Prince (Hexythiazox) was harmless to true spiders; Nadimi *et al.* (2008) validated this finding with *P. persimilis*; and while the two Fenpyroximate products (Acarots and Ortus) showed different effects on true spiders, Acarots was more toxic than Ortus. The present findings are consistent with those published by Blumel and Hausdorf (2002) and Nadimi *et al.* (2008). The highest numbers of individuals (88) recorded in the plot treated with Nest (Abamectin + Spirodiclofen) decreased to 39 individuals in plot treated with Perfect (Abamectin + Chlorfenapyr). These results agreed with Maeyer *et al.* (2002) who proved that Spirodiclofen provided excellent control to *Lepidosaphes ulmi* L. and showed no adverse effect on natural predators of pear psylla (Anthocoridae). While the higher dose of chlorfenapyr (125 g/ha) reduced the predatory population level. In this respect, it is recorded that Nest

had the lowest toxic effect against predators associated with the red spider mite *T. urticae* and was the most toxic pesticide against the red spider mite. In general, the chemical compounds Prince and Acarots revealed high toxic effects against the two spotted spider mite, *T. urticae* and reduced spider population; while the mixture compound Nest, the biochemical Veto and the acaricide Ortus showed the highest total number of individuals of 88, 61, and 50 individuals, respectively with less effective against associated predators. Furthermore, Lagziri and El-Amrani (2009) stated that Abamectin looks to be an excellent choice for strawberry mite management due to its high efficacy, persistence of control, and no detrimental influence on crucial natural enemies. As Abamectin, Fenpyroximate and Biofly are very effective they should be used carefully and may be classified as IPM compatible acaricide in integrated pest management programs against *T. urticae* in Egypt.

6. The Effect of organic and conventional farming on the activity of spider assemblage (Araneae) in some medicinal plants in Fayoum, Egypt:

Organic agriculture is one of these management strategies. This agricultural methodology stresses traditional soil cultivation and production methods while avoiding chemical inputs including artificial fertilizers, insecticides, herbicides, and fungicides (Purgat *et al.*, 2025). According to Wallwork (1976), the usual practice of putting organic and inorganic material to cultivated soils in the form of manure, compost, or fertilizer frequently results in increased soil animal densities and supports greater soil bacterial and fungal activity. Rizk *et al.* (2015) compared the activity density and diversity of true spiders in the conventional plots which

were treated with inorganic fertilizers and sprayed with pesticides where appropriate and the organic plots which fertilized with compost and no sprays were used. Spider activity occurred in three medicinal plants (Wormwood, Chrysanthemum and Spearmint) with organic and inorganic fertility was assessed using pitfall traps in Fayoum, Egypt.

Spider assemblage: Collected spider recorded 737 individuals representing 10 families, 26 genera and 27 species. The 10 families found in the present experiment represent 25 % of the 40 families recorded in Egypt by El-Hennawy (2006).

6.1. Spiders inhabiting land of organic management:

A total of 387 spider species were caught in organic cultivation. They were identified in 7 families and 20 genera and 20 species. The adults averaged 73.4 %. The sex ratio was 2.9 males: 1 female. The most abundant species, *Wadicosa fidelis* (195 individuals), *Pardosa* sp. (89 individuals), *Hogna* sp. (35 individuals), *Thanatus albini* (14 individuals), and *Zelotes* sp (12 individuals), Plots of spearmint and daisy plants received a 151 individuals in both plants, while wormwood showed the lowest number, 85 individuals due to its natural chemical structure which has detergent effect to common pests and in turn the abundance of spiders was reduced. However, wormwood plant had the highest diversity because it had the greatest number of species recorded by 14 individuals while spearmint and daisy plants recorded 12 and 13 species, respectively. Rizk *et al.* (2012) indicated that spider assemblages are highly influenced by variations in plant community structure. Abd El-Karim *et al.* (2016) found that spiders were collected from organic and conventionally grown Chamomile,

Matricaria chamomilla, Chrysanthemum, and *Calendula officinalis*, in two consecutive growth seasons. The results revealed that organic fields collected more spider populations and species than conventional fields. Zaki *et al.* (2021) discovered that organic practices can add diversity to soil structure, enhance the amount of prey, and hence the abundance of spiders. Schmidt *et al.* (2005) and Öberg (2007) observed that spider abundance was higher in organic fields compared to conventional fields. Organic farming has been demonstrated to have a higher richness and diversity of spiders than traditional crop management (Rosas-Ramos *et al.*, 2018; Gallé *et al.*, 2019 and Boeraeve *et al.*, 2022), which is critical for biodiversity conservation and agricultural sustainability.

6.2. Spiders inhabiting land of conventional management:

Rizk *et al.* (2015) found that a total of 350 spider species were caught in the conventional cultivation represented by 10 families, 23 genera and 23 species. Adults averaged 71.7 %. The sex ratio was 2.4 males: 1 female. The most dominant species was *Wadicosa fidelis* (218 individuals), *Pardosa* sp. (46 individuals), *Steatoda erigoniformis* (13 individuals) and *Hogna* sp. (11 individuals). Daisy plants supported a higher abundance of spiders, 137 individuals, while spearmint and wormwood plants of 118 and 95 individuals, respectively. Wormwood plant had little number of spiders but of high diversity which recorded 16 species while daisy and spearmint recorded 15 and 11 individuals, respectively. Schmidt *et al.* (2005) found that most activity density of spiders was in conventional management crops.

- **Species diversity:** Community composition of the organic and the conventional cultivation of collected

spiders were determined using the Shannon-Wiener and Simpson Indices of diversity as calculated and described by Ludwig and Reynolds (1988), the wormwood of conventional cultivation recorded the highest value 1.05 (16 species and 8 families), while daisy of organic cultivation recorded the smallest value 0.57 (13 species and 6 Families). So, we can say that wormwood plants had a higher diversity index than daisy plant; these results go in line with Eyre *et al.* (2008). According to Simpson Index, which reflected the measure of dominance, it was found that the daisy and spearmint plants included the highest number of dominant species in organic cultivation recorded 132 and 129 individuals of Lycosid members, respectively. These results are in good agreement with Bettiol *et al.* (2002) who assumed that the number of collembolans found in the organic system was three times as high as that in the conventional system. So, the organic cultivation included the highest number of dominant species. Also, Abd El-Karim *et al.* (2016) found that spiders were found in abundance on organic plants, with 122 and 147 individuals in chamomile and 157 and 197 in Calendula throughout two seasons. Conventional plants had lower numbers, with 97 and 118 individuals detected in Chamomile and 126 and 171 in Calendula over two seasons, respectively.

7. Spider biodiversity in connection with the vegetation structure and its surrounding soil:

Zaki *et al.* (2020) studied the abundance of spider density and diversity in two different communities, arboreal and ground spiders of four different evergreen shrubs in Orman garden assessed for a whole year using pitfall traps for ground spiders and shaking plants by sweeping net for foliage spiders. Four evergreen shrubs were chosen, red acalypha (*Acalypha*

macrophylla Müll), twisted acalypha (*A. hoffmannii* Müll), single green acalypha (*A. marginata* Müll) and plumbago (*Plumbago auriculata*). Spiders were identified according to different specified keys.

7.1. Species richness of ground spiders:

A total of 45 spiders collected from red acalypha shrubs (9 families., 17g. and 17sp., adults 55.5% and sex ratio was 5.2♂:1♀.). While 50 spiders were collected from twisted acalypha (10 families, 14 g.&14 sp., adults 68%& sex ratio was 2.09♂:1♀) . Green acalypha, recorded the most spiders of 122 individuals (7f., 11g. &11 sp., Juvenile 80.33%, adults 19.67% & sex ratio 1.67♂:1♀). The lowest number of spiders collected from *Plumbago* of 38 spiders, (8 families, 9 genera and 9 species, adults 63.16% and sex ratio 2.4♂:1♀). The most abundant species was *Hogna ferox* recorded 13, 18, 35 and 14 individuals in red acalypha, twisted acalypha, green acalypha and plumbago shrubs, respectively.

7.2. Foliage or arboreal spiders:

Total of 43 spiders were collected from red acalypha shrubs, (5 families. 14 genera and 14 species), twisted acalypha registered 40 spiders, red acalypha (7 families, 9 genera and 12 species), green acalypha of 32 spiders (4 families, 8 genera and 10 species), while highest number of spiders collected from plumbago shrubs of 95 spiders (7 families, 15 genera and 19 species). The most abundant species was *Philodromus* sp. 11 and 20 individuals collected from red acalypha and plumbago shrubs, respectively; while species *Cheiracanthium* was the most abundant in twisted acalypha and green acalypha (10 and 7 individuals), respectively.

7.3. Rank abundance of spider families:

A total of 255 individuals were collected from ground spiders, while

only 210 individuals from foliage spiders. The most abundant families of ground spiders represented by family Lycosidae 158 individuals (61.96 %), while those of vegetation represented by family Salticidae 70 individuals (33.33%) Vegetation spiders were more diverse and more active than ground spiders.

7.4. Relative abundance and frequency of spider communities:

7.4.1. Ground spiders:

According to Weis Fogh system of classification, members of family Lycosidae were considered accessory in red acalypha, twisted acalypha and Plumbago registered 44.44, 48, and 36.84%, respectively, while recorded 81.97 % in green acalypha and considered as constant. According to Weigmann classification of dominance, members of family Salticidae: *P. paykulli* and *H. adansoni* considered as dominant, this result agrees with that of Shuang-Lin and Bo-Ping (2006) and Abd El-Karim *et al.* (2016) who indicated that Lycosidae was the dominant family and occupied more than 60% of ground spider community.

7.4.2. Leaves or arboreal spiders:

According "Weis Fogh system of frequency" members of family Salticidae were "Constant" 59.38% on leaves of single green acalypha. According to Weigmann dominance, the most dominant species recorded in members of family Salticidae under green acalypha and twisted acalypha as considered 'Eudominant". Plumbago shrubs seemed to have a higher amount of diversity than the three types of acalypha, because it had the greatest number of species.

8. True spiders inhabiting ornamental trees, flowering annuals and herbs:

Zaki *et al.* (2020) clarifies the relationship between spider density, diversity and habitat structure measured for a whole year by comparing the

spider fauna on three tree species Severinia, (*Severinia monophylla* L.); dombeya, (*Dombeya wallichii* Lind.) and feijoa, (*Feijoa sellowiana*), and on the flowering annuals (*Crinum asiaticum* L.) and the evergreen herbs (*Pelargonium geranium* Bailly). Two methods were used for capturing spiders, by using pitfall traps for ground spiders and shaking plants on a sweeping net for aerial spiders.

8.1. Species richness of the ground spiders:

8.1.1. Spiders under the three trees:

A total of 33 spiders were collected from microhabitat under severinia trees, represented 8 families, 14 genera and 14 species, adults of 60.61%. While a total of 42 spiders collected under dombeya tree, included 6 families, 10 genera and 10 species, adults of 76.19%. Moreover, a total of 42 spiders captured from microhabitat of feijoa tree; registered 9 families, 15 genera and 15 species, while adults were 76.19%. The most abundance species collected under the three mentioned trees was *H. ferox* recorded 9, 13 and 13 individuals of severinia, dombeya and feijoa, %, respectively

8.1.2. Spiders of evergreen herbs

***Pelargonium*:**

A total of 45 spiders were collected from pelargonium, represented by 5 families, 8 genera and 8 species, adults average 86.67%, the most abundance species was *H. ferox* (19 individuals)

8.1.3. Spiders of flowering *Crinum*:

A total of 37 spiders collected from crinum, represented 7 families, 10 genera and 10 species adults average 48.65%, of the most abundant species was *H. adansoni* (12 individuals) followed by *H. ferox* (11 individuals).

8.2. Species richness of the foliage spiders:

8.2.1. Spiders inhabiting foliage of trees:

A total of 30 spiders collected from foliage of *severinia* tree. They represented by 6 families, 9 genera and 13 species, adults average 46.6%. The most abundant species was *Theridion* sp. (7 individuals) followed by *Philodromus* sp. (6 individuals).

A total of 12 spiders collected from *Dombeya* leaves, represented by 5 families, 8 genera and 9 species, adults average 41.67%, the most abundant species was *Thomisus* sp. (3 individuals).

8.2.2. Spiders inhabiting foliage of *Pelargonium*:

A total of 41 spiders were collected from *pelargonium* represented by 7 families, 14 genera and 16 species, adults of 36.59%, the most abundant species was *Philodromus* sp. (10 individuals).

8.2.3. Spiders inhabiting foliage of *Crinum*:

A total of 11 spiders were collected from *crinum*, they represented by 4 families, 8 genera and 8 species, adults of 18.18%, the most abundance species was *Philodromus* sp.

8.3. Relative abundance-frequency of spider communities:

8.3.1. Ground spiders:

According to Weis Fogh frequency classification, members of Lycosidae were considered constant (C) species in abundance under *fejjoa* tree and *pelargonium* herb which recorded 52.38 and 84.44%, respectively. According to Weis Fogh system, family Lycosidae was considered "Constant" 84.44% in *pelargonium* and "Accessory" 32.43% in *crinum*, while family Salticidae was considered "Accessory" 48.65% in *crinum*.

8.3.2. Foliage spiders:

By Weis Fogh system" family Therididae and Philodromidae considered accessory (40.00% and 26.67%), respectively in *Severinia*. Members of family Theridiidae were

"Dominant" on leaves of *severinia*. While

family Salticidae was "Dominant".

According to Weis Fogh system. Family Philodromidae and Thrediidae were considered "Accessory" (34.15% and 26.83%), respectively in *pelargonium* family Salticidae was considered "Constant" in *Crinum*.

8.3.3. Spider diversity:

The highest value of index "H" recorded in ground spiders under *fejjoa* (2.32) followed in *severinia* of value (2.21). But the lowest "H" value recorded (1.44) in *pelargonium* (Evergreen herbs), while leaves spiders, revealed the highest "H" value recorded in *pelargonium* (2.43), then *Crinum* of value (2.02). According to Simpson "S" index, the highest value recorded in ground spider under *pelargonium* (0.31) flower.

9. Effect of the vegetation density of some flowers and shrubs on the abundance and the diversity of spiders:

Ghallab *et al.* (2021) studied the spider's diversity and their distribution in the flower category was of low elevation (0.75–1.5 m) included six species, *Dimorphotheca pulvialis* L., *Salvia splendens* L., *Helichrysum bracteatum* (Vent.), *Tagetes erecta* L., *Chrysanthemum coronarium* L. and *Crinum asiaticum* L.; while the shrubs were four species of high elevation (1–2.5m). They were *Acalypha macrophylla* Müll, *A. marginata* Müll, *A. hoffmanii* Müll and *Plumbago auriculata* Lam. Foliage spiders were collected by shaking plants on the sweeping net then preserved in 70% ethyl alcohol and some droplets of glycerine.

9.1. Species richness of spiders inhabiting flowers:

A total of 130 individuals represented 10 families, 19 genera and 21 species. The most common families Thomisidae (38.5%), Salticidae

(16.2%) and Theridiidae (15.4%) accounted for 70 % of all spiders. The *Helichrysum* and *Chrysanthemum* flowers appeared to be a suitable dweller for foliage spiders, they recorded the highest collection of spiders of 33 and 29 individual respectively of the total 130 individuals included the most abundant species, *Thomisus spinifer* (Thomisidae) was common in the garden for the abundance of flowers. It was collected from *Helichrysum* (75.8%), *Dimorphotheca* (50%), *Tagetes* (42.8%) *Salvia* and *Chrysanthemum* 25 and 24.1% respectively. The height of the two plants (Up to one meter) and the structure of leaves and dense vegetation might be a reason for spiders' abundance. This observation in accordance with that of Corcuera *et al.* (2008). In contrast, *Tagetes* and *Crinum* flowers of low elevation, recorded 14 and 11 individuals, respectively. *Crinum* plant recorded 4 species of Salticidae of 72.2%, the low elevation of this plant as well as the lack of poor branches, probably be a reason to distribute species of Salticidae which were abundant in leaf litter beneath plants.

9.2. Species richness of spiders inhabiting shrubs:

A total of 127 individuals representing 6 families, 13 genera and 13 species were obtained; the most common family was Salticidae (35.4%), followed by Philodromidae (20.5%) then Cheiracanthiidae (17.3%), those families accounted 73 % of all spiders sampled; the least common family was Araneidae comprising (2.4%). As for preference of the shrub structure and the spider abundance, the three common species selected of *Acalypha* were of dense vegetation as well as broad leaves, the abundance of spiders in the three plants species was close, recorded 28, 27 and 25 for species *macrophylla*, *marginata* and *hoffmanii*, respectively.

Plumbago shrub distinguished by loose branchlets with small leaves. It was invaded by 47 individuals, (8 species of 6 families). This result is in conformity with that of Ghallab (2013) which proved that foliage runner spiders were the dominant on *Lantana* shrubs which had few branches.

9.3. Foraging guild:

Six functional groups based on their foraging behavior in the field (Uetz *et al.*, 1999), they are stalkers, ambushers, foliage runners, orb web, space weavers and wandering sheets

9.3.1. In the floral, plants:

The ambusher (Thomisidae (38.5%) was the dominant on flora. This observation is in accordance with Ceballos *et al.* (2004).

9.3.2. According to shrub category:

The stalkers (Salticidae) were predominant (35.4%) of the total spider this result was in accordance with Labanon and Nuñez (2020), they proved that jumping spiders can found in all ecosystems with a broad range of microhabitats from beneath leaf litter. Orb weaver guild was the least frequent in both flora and shrubs categories, recording 2.3 and 2.4 %, respectively, the foliage running spiders (Cheiracanthidae) depend on vegetation for finding food; they recorded 10.8 and 17.3% in flora and shrubs, respectively. The flora recorded the highest species richness (21 species) while shrubs recorded (13 species). The guild composition in the different species of flora and shrubs were definitely different which indicates the high difference between their habitats.

9.4. Spider's diversity:

9.4.1. Biodiversity of spider species in the flowers category:

The biodiversity index calculation (H') indicated that the *Chrysanthemum* and *Salvia* flowers were the most diverse, their values (1.7 and 1.6), respectively, both recorded 10 species of 7 families. The lowest spider diverse

was observed in *Helichrysum* and *Crinum* flowers of values 0.8 and 0.7 and both of 6 species belonged to 5 and 3 families. According to Simpson Index, (Measure of dominance), *Helichrysum* flowers included the highest number of dominant species *Thomisus spinifer* of value (0.59) which was 75.8% of the total spiders.

9.4.2. Biodiversity of spider species in the shrubs category:

The biodiversity index of spider species in different structures of the four previously mentioned shrubs of biggest values, 1.5 for both shrubs which indicates the most diverse; the *A. macrophylla* comprised 10 species of 5 families where *Plumbago* includes 8 species of 6 families. According to Simpson Index, *A. marginata* shrub included the highest number of dominant species (0.5), it was for members of Salticidae and Cheiracanthidae 66.7% and 22.2% , respectively.

9.5. Faunal similarity of spiders:

To allow a comparison of similarity between the habitats of the flowers and the shrubs, the Sørensen's quotient of similarity (QS) was calculated. It is concluded that the two communities were semi-similar as they recorded 65% of similarity.

10. Seasonal abundance of true spiders inhabiting perennial shrubs and evergreen herbs:

Ismail *et al.* (2021) compared activity of spider inhabiting two categories of ornamental plants, the first group, three herbs: *Ruscus aculeatus* L., *Pelargonium zonal* (Hertier) and *Ocimum basilicum* L., and the second, three shrubs: *Plumbago auriculata* Lam., *Acalypha hoffmannii* Müll and *Dodonaea viscosa* Jacq. Moreover, they surveyed spiders on different vegetation. The experiment was conducted for a whole year. A total of 694 spiders collected forming at least

42 species belonging to 33 genera in 15 families.

10.1. Spiders inhabiting shrubs:

A total of 255 spiders were collected from *Plumbago*, *Acalifa* and *Dodonaea* shrubs belonged to 10 families, 20 genera and 23 species. The most abundant species were 89 individuals of *Pulchellodromus* (Philodromidae), 25 of *Cheiracanthium* (Miturgiidae) 24 of *Thomisus spinifer* (Salticidae), 24 of *Theridion* (Theridiidae), and 22 of *Thyene* (Salticidae).

10.2. Spiders inhabiting herbs:

A total of 261 spiders collected, classified into 10 families, 21 genera and 25 species; the most abundant families were Philodromidae represented 66.2, 35.9 and 31.2% in *Ruscus*, *Pelargonium* and *Ocimum* herbs, respectively, followed by Theridiidae 28.2% collected from *Pelargonium* then Salticidae 22.1% from *Ocimum* then Thomisidae 20.8% and Theridiidae 18.2% collected from *Ocimum*.

10.3. Survey of spider on different plants:

A total of 178 spiders collected from thirty ornamental plants belonged to 13 families, 28 genera and at least 35 species. The most abundant families were Thomisidae 24.2%, Salticidae 23% and Theridiidae 23% then Philodromidae 10.7%, adults of 59.6%, (31.5% ♂: 28.1% ♀). The most dominant species were *T.spinifer* (35 individuals) followed by *K. aulica* (27 individuals).

10.4. Family richness and generic diversity:

Fifteen families were collected, the most dominant: Salticidae (8 genera and 9 species), Theridiidae (4 genera and 7 species), Thomisidae (2 genera and 4 species), Araneidae (3 genera and 3 species), Philodromidae (3 genera and 3 species), Lycosidae (2 genera and 2 species),

10.5. Rank abundance of spider families:

Five families contained 93.1% of the total collected spiders; they were Philodromidae (36.7%), Salticidae (20.2%), Theridiidae (17.3%), Thomisidae (12.5%) and Cheiracanthiidae (6.5%). The greatest number of individuals was found in the family Philodromidae (255 individuals), then Salticidae (140), Theridiidae (120), Thomisidae (87) and Cheiracanthiidae (44).

10.6. Spider guild composition:

Eight feeding guilds recorded, the (Ambushers) was the dominant on the three categories recorded 50.2, 58.2% and 34.8% in shrubs, herbs and different vegetation, respectively, followed by the stalkers then space weavers, foliage runners, orb weavers, ground runners, sheet web and scattered-line web.

10.7. Faunal similarity of spiders:

The species richness of spiders collected from shrubs was (255 individuals of 23 species) and that of herbs was (261 individuals of 25 species), to allow a comparison between the habitats of the two categories, the Sørensen (1948) quotient of similarity (QS) was calculated; the community of shrubs and that of herbs have a high overlap as they recorded 80% of similarity. The interaction of different communities of spider abundance and species richness depends on the type of plant dense vegetation, shade, and humidity; so, a slight difference was observed between different categories located in the same location (Ghallab, 2012).

10.8. Spider's diversity:

The biodiversity index of different vegetation was the most diverse recorded value (1.9), followed by shrubs (1.5). According to Simpson Index, it was found that diversity of spiders in herbs included the highest number of dominant species (0.33).

Diversity generally increases when a greater variety of habitat types are present (Ried and Miller, 1989 and Sudhikumar *et al.*, 2005).

11. The effect of Agricultural Practices Methods on spider species diversity:

11.1. Tillage, no tillage:

Rizk *et al.* (2017) found that farming alerts the physical, chemical, and biological components of the soil system. No-till, direct-drill methods produce considerable variations in soil organism activity as compared to typical deeper tillage. Rizk and Mikhail (1999) discovered that higher activity densities of soil fauna species were often related with no-tillage techniques, a finding confirmed by Wardle *et al.* (2006). Also, Rizk and Mikhail (1999) discovered that spiders disappeared after ploughing but reappeared after tomato planting. Also, Gupta (1994) stated that conventional tillage allows organisms to spread deeper into the ploughed layer. Because of increased soil stubble contact, residue breakdown and nutrient mineralization occur more quickly. Annual plowing reduces spider diversity (Haskins and Shaddy, 1986).

11.2. Soil solarization:

Rizk, *et al.* (2017), a significant disadvantage of this technology (Solarization) is its reliance on climate. Soil solarization was utilized to manage root knot nematodes, soil-borne illnesses, root rot disease, and weeds. Solarization is a way of controlling soil biota with solar heat that does not use pesticides or hazardous materials. This strategy is inexpensive and simply applied in Mediterranean and tropical climates with scorching summers. Solarization can have a positive, negative, or neutral impact on pest-soil fauna and biological control interactions. It will also have an impact on the populations and distribution patterns of trophic (Functional) groups among soil animals (Rizk, 2002). Soil

solarization reduced the total amount of soil fauna because it raised soil temperature, which often reduces soil fauna diversity, particularly for heat-constrained species (Rizk, *et al.*, 2017). Vats and Narula (1993) discovered that the population density of Acarina was positively associated with temperature. Rizk (2002) discovered that spider populations declined from 30 individuals in fallow plots to 27 in cultivated areas and only 4 in polarized plots.

12. Monthly fluctuation of spider population:

Ghallab (2012) found that the high monthly population of spiders collected in early summer during May followed by June, while the lowest population were recorded during February and March. Also, Rizk *et al.* (2012) spiders appeared in few numbers in early summer, the population density gradually increased showing a peak in June. In general, data indicated that spiders were active during summer months. These studies show that plant density of vegetation, altitude and structures of plants affected spider diversity and activity density. Seasonal effects on field spiders differ depending on location, crop type, and climatic factors, with peak numbers typically occurring in late summer/early autumn in the Northern Hemisphere and during specific growth seasons, such as the Rabi season in some countries. Climate variables such as temperature and relative humidity, the availability of prey like aphids, and the physical structure of the field environment all have an impact on spider abundance (Obuid-Allah *et al.*, 2017). Seasonal factors such as temperature, rainfall, and humidity have a significant impact on spider populations and community composition in agricultural fields. Higher temperatures and humidity encourage spider activity and population growth, whereas periods of

heavy rain or extreme dryness can reduce abundance. Peak spider activity is typically observed during the growing seasons (e.g., spring and late summer/early autumn), which are marked by favorable climatic conditions; nevertheless, dry or wet seasons may result in a reduced spider fauna.

Mushtaq *et al.* (2000), Ghallab (2013), Abd El-Karim *et al.* (2016) and Zaki *et al.* (2020) all affirmed that the highest monthly spider count was in early summer during May, with the lowest numbers observed in February. This conclusion is consistent with the findings of Abdel Moneim *et al.* (2003), who discovered that summer was the season of greatest abundance for spiders, with no significant variations across locations, although substantial differences were detected between months of the year independent of site. Similar findings were reported by Uetz (1975) and Jiang and Bo-Ping (2006), who discovered that most spiders were trapped during the summer months. Furthermore, Rizk *et al.* (2015) confirmed this finding, reporting that monthly counts of spiders collected from organic and conventional cultivations between October and the first week of May showed a high abundance in March, with 109 individuals and three egg sacs for organic cultivation and 88 individuals and one egg sac for conventional cultivation. Mushtaq *et al.* (2000) reported similar findings, noting that the highest number of foliage spider species was found in a monthly sample taken in May. These findings are consistent with Ghallab (2013), who found that total monthly counts of spiders collected from Croton trees were highest in early summer during May and lowest in February. She also discovered that the highest numbers of spiders on Lantana plants were collected in May and June, with the

lowest numbers recorded in December, January, and February.

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